

A S4D ablation study

We describe the experiments conducted on S4D that inspired the architecture of the proposed RSSM block.

Our RSSM block does not include a mixing layer (Figure 3) that combines the H features at each step of the output sequence generated by the convolutional layer. We made this architectural choice (Figure 2) because, without proper training, a mixing layer ruins the dynamics of the individual features in the output signal.

Fig. 2: Graphical comparison of a single S4 block (left) and a single RSSM block (right). In the RSSM block, the mixing layer is removed to simplify the model and enhance its efficiency. Only the nonlinear activation function is retained, streamlining the architecture while maintaining essential functionality.

In our model, feature mixing is implicitly handled by the encoder through the \mathbf{W}_{en} matrix, which combines the original H_0 features of the input signal. Learning how the features depend on each other is left to the readout model, which operates in a high-dimensional space. To demonstrate that the untrained mixing layer ruins the dynamics of individual features of the output signal, we conduct an ablation study on the S4D model to identify which parameters can be fixed without significantly affecting performance. We fix the sampling frequency Δ time and, in succession, the encoder, the parameters \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{D} of the S4D block, and the mixing layer within the S4D block. The mixing layer learns the dependencies between the features (Figure 3) [22] to overcome the fact that the S4 and S4D models are single input and single output (SISO), unlike S5, which performs a scan with an associative binary operation, in parallel [51].

Fig. 3: Graphical representation of the mixing layer. The mixing layer combines the features at each timestep independently of the other timesteps in the sequence. When trained, it can provide an advantage; otherwise, it disrupts the dynamics produced by the independent H SSMs that process the features independently (Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Graphical representation of the H independent SSM, one for each feature of the input sequence. The internal state of each SSM is a vector of dimension P . The output signal has the same number of features H as the input signal.

We notice that freezing parameters **B**, **C**, and **D** degrades the performance of the SSM very slightly. Freezing matrix **A** can cause performance degradation that we can avoid with a good choice of A eigenvalues.

Instead, fixing the mixing layer causes a high degradation as it ruins the trajectories over time of each feature $y(t)$ (Figure 3). Therefore, we obtain the best performance by removing the mixing layer (Table 5 and Figure 2) because the original input signal features are already mixed by the matrix \mathbf{W}_{en} . Moreover, the readout model can then specifically learn the feature dependencies in the output signal generated by the reservoir, independent of the temporal dependencies.

Table 5: Ablation study on the S4D model. The symbol * stands for an untrained parameter. The last three rows represent untrained S4D blocks, where only the decoder layer is trained. These experiments are run on sMNIST with a small S4D model with two layers of 64 features H .

Δ Encoder	A	B	C	D	Mixing Layer	Accuracy
*						98.23
*	*					98.63
*	*	*				98.20
*	*	*	*			97.67
*	*	*	*	*		96.89
*	*	*	*	*	*	97.58
*	*	*	*	*	reservoir+glu	73.17
*	*	*	*	*	reservoir+tanh	69.84
*	*	*	*	*	identity	78.75

B Training pipeline

Our model efficiently uses both CPU and GPU processing units. Initially, input data is transferred to the GPU’s dedicated memory (VRAM) to take advantage of the parallelization capabilities of convolutional operations by processing input sequences in batches on the GPU. Once the GPU completes its computations, to manage the limited memory available on GPUs VRAM, we transfer each batched global output $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times nH \times L}$, generated by the RSSM (Equation 6), back to the system’s main memory RAM. This transfer enables the CPU to collect the outputs to form a new input dataset $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times nH \times L}$, where N represents the total number of time series (see Figure 5). This dataset, together with the original labels, is prepared for a data loader. The data loader is responsible for moving each batch (which may vary in size from B) back to the GPU, where a readout neural network is trained (as shown in Figures 1 and 5).

Fig. 5: Graphical representation of the RSSM forward phase. Input data is transferred to the GPU’s VRAM for parallel processing in the convolutional RSSM blocks. For memory efficiency, the outputs are moved to the system’s RAM via the CPU, then transferred back to the GPU in batches for training the readout model. The batch size for the frozen RSSM is chosen to speed up the forward phase, while the readout model’s batch size is chosen to maximize accuracy through standard model selection.

To train the readout model, the first w timesteps from each time series \mathbf{y} may be discarded for general tasks, as they are less representative of the series’ dynamics. For the classification task, by setting $w = L - 1$, we use only the last timestep \mathbf{y}_{L-1} , being the most representative of the series as it encapsulates all preceding information.

The readout can be a sequence modeling neural network, such as an RNN, a 1-D convolutional network, or a trainable SSM, trained on the input dataset $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times nH \times (L-w)}$. Alternatively, for greater efficiency, we use a readout model that treats each timestep independently, without temporal or sequential dependencies like a closed-form readout such as ridge regression or a feed-forward neural network such as MLP. In this case, the readout is trained on the input dataset $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N(L-w) \times nH}$, among the vector of labels $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^{N(L-w)}$.

We choose to use the MLP or the ridge regression as readout to maximize the information and expressiveness of the global RSSM output while keeping the training phase more efficient (for complexity analysis, see Section 4.4 and Table 1).

More in detail, given the vector of labels $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^{N(L-w)}$, the ridge regression readout solves the l_2 regularized least-squares problem [38]:

$$\mathbf{W}_{out} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{W}} \{ \|\mathbf{Y} \cdot \mathbf{W} - \mathbf{d}\|^2 + \alpha \|\mathbf{W}\|^2 \} \quad (13)$$

in closed form

$$\mathbf{W}_{out} = (\mathbf{Y}^T \mathbf{Y} + \alpha \mathbf{I})^{-1} \mathbf{Y}^T \mathbf{d}. \quad (14)$$

C RSSM parameters

The parameters of the RSSM include the encoding matrix $\mathbf{W}_{en} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times H}$ for the encoding layer and the parameters of each RSSM block, obtained from a discretized continuous SSM.

The \mathbf{W}_{en} matrix encodes the original input signal $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times L}$ in a output signal $\mathbf{y}^{(0)}$ with H features. For each time step l , the features of $\mathbf{y}_l^{(0)}$ are given by the linear combination of the features of \mathbf{u}_l with the rows of \mathbf{W}_{en} as coefficients. We fix the parameter $\mathbf{W}_{en} \in \mathbb{R}^{H_0 \times H}$ such that each value has an absolute value in the interval $[m_{en}, M_{en}]$ where m_{en} and M_{en} are positive values. Recall that \mathbf{W}_{en} have real values, so they can take values in $[-M_{en}, -m_{en}] \cup [m_{en}, M_{en}]$. Having the real values of \mathbf{W}_{en} different signs helps to mix better the features of the original input signals and avoid exploding values of the encoded input $\mathbf{y}^{(0)}$ obtainable with all positive or all negative values of \mathbf{W}_{en} .

C.1 RSSM block

The parameters of the RSSM block consist of the diagonal state matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H}$, the vector of the sampling rates $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^H$, the input matrix $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H}$, the output matrix $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{H \times P}$, and the skip connection vector $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^H$. We recall that the parameters ($\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H}$, $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^H$, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H}$, $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{H \times P}$, $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^H$) identify H independent continuous SSMs, one for each feature $i = 0, \dots, H-1$ as we can see in Equation 15 and Figure 4

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} &= [\mathbf{A}_0 | \dots | \mathbf{A}_{H-1}], \quad \mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{B}_0 | \dots | \mathbf{B}_{H-1}] \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H} \\ \mathbf{C} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_0 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_{H-1} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{H \times P}, \\ \mathbf{D} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}_0 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{D}_{H-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Delta = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_0 \\ \vdots \\ \Delta_{H-1} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^H. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The state matrix \mathbf{A} has a crucial role in determining the internal dynamics of our models since it regulates the relationship between successive internal states over time. We fix the state matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{0,0} & \dots & \lambda_{0,H-1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \lambda_{P-1,0} & \dots & \lambda_{P-1,H-1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

of the H continuous SSMs randomly in the space

$$\{\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H} \mid m_{\mathbf{A}} \leq \Re(\lambda_{i,j}) \leq M_{\mathbf{A}}, 0 \leq \Im(\lambda_{i,j}) < 2\pi\}. \quad (17)$$

The hyperparameters $m_{\mathbf{A}}$, $M_{\mathbf{A}}$, referring to the minimum and maximum values of the real parts of the complex eigenvalues of state matrix \mathbf{A} , control the internal stability of the RSSM (for more details see the Section 4.1).

The vector $\Delta \in \mathbb{R}^H$ represents the sampling rates for each input feature, used to discretize the H continuous systems into H discrete-time systems. We set the hyperparameters m_{Δ} and M_{Δ} that constraints the value of each Δ_i :

$$\Delta \in [m_{\Delta}, M_{\Delta}]^H \subset \mathbb{R}^H, \quad \text{with } M_{\Delta} \geq m_{\Delta} > 0. \quad (18)$$

The input matrix \mathbf{B} and the output matrix \mathbf{C} are crucial in defining the relationship between the state and observations. Specifically, the input matrix \mathbf{B} maps the control inputs, regulating to what extent the control inputs affect the internal dynamics. On the other hand, the output matrix \mathbf{C} links the internal state of the system to the observable outputs, thereby determining how the state is reflected in the measurements. We fix the parameters $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times H}$ and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{H \times P}$ of the H continuous SSMs such that each value has an absolute value in the interval $[m_{\mathbf{B}}, M_{\mathbf{B}}]$ and $[m_{\mathbf{C}}, M_{\mathbf{C}}]$ respectively, where $m_{\mathbf{B}}$, $m_{\mathbf{C}}$, $M_{\mathbf{B}}$ and $M_{\mathbf{C}}$ are positive values. \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} having complex values assume values belonging to the ring $\{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid m_{\mathbf{B}} \leq \|z\| \leq M_{\mathbf{B}}\}$ and $\{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid m_{\mathbf{C}} \leq \|z\| \leq M_{\mathbf{C}}\}$ respectively.

The skip connection parameter $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^H$ operates feature-wise, adding to each output feature i the respective input feature scaled by \mathbf{D}_i . We set its values in the interval $[m_{\mathbf{D}}, M_{\mathbf{D}}]$ where $M_{\mathbf{D}} > m_{\mathbf{D}}$ are real values. In this way, having the possibility to set the parameter \mathbf{D} values to be all positive, all negative, or with mixed signs, we have more control over the skip connection.

D Definitions

In this appendix, we provide comprehensive background definitions of the main concepts used in this work. We start with the definition of a continuous-time state space model and its discretization through the Zero-Order Hold (ZOH) transform. We then define the convolution kernel associated with the discrete state space model.

Definition 2 (Continuous State Space Model (SSM)). *A continuous SSM is a parameterized linear time-invariant system defined by*

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}'(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ y(t) = \Re(\mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{D}u(t), \quad t \in \mathbb{R}_+. \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^P$ is the internal state, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the input, $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the output. The model parameters are the state matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P}$, the input matrix $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times 1}$, the output matrix $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times P}$, and the skip connection $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}$.

Definition 3 (Discrete State Space Model (SSM)). *The discrete SSM is*

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}_k = \bar{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x}_{k-1} + \bar{\mathbf{B}}u_k \\ y_k = \Re(\bar{\mathbf{C}}\mathbf{x}_k) + \bar{\mathbf{D}}u_k, \quad k = 0, \dots, L-1 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where the new parameters $\bar{\mathbf{A}}, \bar{\mathbf{B}}, \bar{\mathbf{C}}, \bar{\mathbf{D}}$ are obtained by a discretization method, e.g., ZOH (Definition 4), using a constant sampling frequency Δ .

Definition 4 (Zero-Order Hold (ZOH) Transform). Given a continuous SSM (Definition 2) and sampling interval $\Delta > 0$, the Zero-Order Hold (ZOH) transform maps the continuous system to the discrete SSM (Definition 3) where the discrete parameters are given by

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\mathbf{A}} = e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}} \\ \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} (e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{B} \\ \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{C} \\ \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \mathbf{D} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

with $e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}}$ denoting the matrix exponential and \mathbf{I} the identity matrix.

Definition 5 (SSM Convolution Kernel). Given a discrete SSM (Definition 3), the convolution kernel $\bar{\mathbf{K}} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times L}$ is defined as

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}} = [\bar{\mathbf{C}}\bar{\mathbf{B}}, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{C}}\bar{\mathbf{A}}^l\bar{\mathbf{B}}, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{C}}\bar{\mathbf{A}}^{L-1}\bar{\mathbf{B}}] \quad (22)$$

where L is the sequence length. The kernel $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ defines the linear convolution mapping from the input sequence u_k to the output sequence y_k , obtained by unrolling the recurrence of the discrete SSM (Definition 3):

$$y_k = \Re \left(\sum_{l=0}^k \bar{\mathbf{K}}_l u_{k-l} \right) + \bar{\mathbf{D}} u_k. \quad (23)$$

Definition 6 (Convolution Kernel for Diagonal Discrete SSM). Let $\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \text{diag}(\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{P-1}) \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P}$ be a diagonal state matrix, $\bar{\mathbf{B}} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times 1}$ the input matrix, and $\bar{\mathbf{C}} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times P}$ the output matrix. The convolution kernel $\bar{\mathbf{K}} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times L}$ in Definition 5 can be written as:

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}} = (\bar{\mathbf{C}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T) \cdot \mathbf{V}, \quad (24)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times L}$ is the Vandermonde matrix generated by $(\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{P-1})$, with entries $\mathbf{V}_{i,l} = \lambda_i^l$

Definition 7 (Convolution View of SSM). Given a discrete SSM (Definition 3), the kernel $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ (Definition 5) defines the linear convolution mapping from the input sequence $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times L}$ to the output sequence $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times L}$

$$\mathbf{y} = \Re (\bar{\mathbf{K}} * \mathbf{u}) + \bar{\mathbf{D}} \mathbf{u}. \quad (25)$$

The linear convolution is computed using the discrete Fourier transform (DFT):

$$\mathbf{y} = \Re (DFT^{-1} (DFT (\bar{\mathbf{K}}) \odot DFT (\mathbf{u}))) + \bar{\mathbf{D}} \mathbf{u}. \quad (26)$$

E Proofs

This appendix provides proofs for the theorems and lemmas presented in the main text. For all the proofs, we assume the number of features $H = 1$ for simplicity. This assumption does not affect the generality of the results, as each feature is processed independently in the RSSM layer.

Theorem 1: Stability Conditions. A deep RSSM architecture is stable if all of its constituent RSSM blocks are stable. An RSSM block is stable if and only if each of the H discretised SSMs is stable. A continuous SSM is stable if and only if $\Re(\lambda_i) \leq 0$, and equivalently, a discretized SSM is stable if and only if $\rho_i \leq 1$

Proof. First, we note that a hierarchy of contractive reservoirs is stable [16]. Second, we note that for a diagonal state space matrix, the eigenvalues coincide with the singular values. Therefore, the spectral norm coincides with the spectral radius. Hence, if the spectral radius is less than 1, then the corresponding dynamics are contractive. Moreover, an RSSM block is composed of H independent SSM systems. With these remarks, it now suffices to find conditions of stability for a single SSM to imply the stability of a deep RSSM architecture. Let $\mathbf{A} = \text{diag}(\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_P) \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times P}$ be a diagonal continuous-time state matrix. The continuous-time SSM is stable if and only if the real part of every eigenvalue is non-positive, i.e., $\Re(\lambda_i) \leq 0$ for all i (see, e.g., [33, 46, 26]).

Consider the discretization of the system with sampling interval $\Delta > 0$. The discretized state matrix is given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}} = \exp(\Delta \mathbf{A}) = \text{diag}(e^{\Delta \lambda_0}, \dots, e^{\Delta \lambda_P}).$$

Let $\bar{\lambda}_i = e^{\Delta \lambda_i}$ denote the i -th eigenvalue of $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$. The modulus of $\bar{\lambda}_i$ is

$$\rho_i = |\bar{\lambda}_i| = |e^{\Delta \lambda_i}| = e^{\Delta \Re(\lambda_i)}.$$

The discrete-time SSM is stable if and only if $|\bar{\lambda}_i| \leq 1$ for all i (see, e.g., [31, 45]). This is equivalent to

$$e^{\Delta \Re(\lambda_i)} \leq 1 \iff \Delta \Re(\lambda_i) \leq 0.$$

Since $\Delta > 0$, this holds if and only if $\Re(\lambda_i) \leq 0$ for all i .

Therefore, the stability condition for the continuous SSM ($\Re(\lambda_i) \leq 0$) is equivalent to the stability condition for the discretized SSM ($\rho_i \leq 1$).

Lemma 1: State Dimension Effect. The state dimension P determines the number of oscillatory terms in $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$. Higher P allows for more complex filters by superposition of diverse frequencies.

Proof. The pre-activated output of the RSSM layer is given by

$$\mathbf{y} = \Re \left(DFT^{-1} \left(DFT(\bar{\mathbf{K}}) \odot DFT(\mathbf{u}) \right) \right) + \bar{\mathbf{D}}\mathbf{u}, \quad (27)$$

where DFT is the discrete Fourier transform and DFT^{-1} is its inverse. Assuming the skip connection $\bar{\mathbf{D}} = 0$, we can rewrite the Equation 27 as

$$\mathbf{y} = \Re(\bar{\mathbf{K}} * \mathbf{u}) = \Re(\bar{\mathbf{K}}) * \mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{F}} * \mathbf{u},$$

where we denote the convolution filter as $\bar{\mathbf{F}} = \Re(\bar{\mathbf{K}})$. The kernel $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ is given by $\bar{\mathbf{K}} = (\bar{\mathbf{C}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T) \cdot \mathbf{V}$, where \mathbf{V} is the Vandermonde matrix of $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$. To simplify, we define the vector $\mathbf{W} = \bar{\mathbf{C}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T$. The l -th element of the kernel $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ is given by the dot product $\mathbf{W} \cdot \bar{\mathbf{A}}^l$. Rewriting \mathbf{W} and $\bar{\mathbf{A}}^l$ in polar notation:

$$\mathbf{W} = \bar{\mathbf{C}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T = [\nu_0 e^{i\psi_0} \dots \nu_P e^{i\psi_P}]$$

and

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}}^l = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_0^l e^{i(l\theta_0)} \\ \vdots \\ \rho_P^l e^{i(l\theta_P)} \end{bmatrix},$$

the l -th element of the kernel becomes $\bar{\mathbf{K}}_l = \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \rho_i^l \cdot e^{i(\psi_i + l\theta_i)}$. Thus, the l -th element of the convolution filter is:

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l = \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \rho_i^l \cdot \cos(\psi_i + l\theta_i).$$

The convolution filter $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ is equivalent to a sum of P oscillatory components, where P is the state dimension of the SSM:

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}} = \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \bar{\mathbf{F}}^{(i)}.$$

Therefore, the i -th oscillatory component is $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{(i)} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times L}$, with the l -th element $\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l^{(i)} = \nu_i \rho_i^l \cos(\psi_i + l\theta_i)$. Each component $\bar{\mathbf{F}}^{(i)}$ is characterized by its amplitude ν_i , decay rate ρ_i , phase ψ_i , and frequency θ_i .

Lemma 2: Stability Constraint. The $\Re(\lambda_i)$, affecting the decay/growth rates ρ_i , govern both the memory capacity and the stability of the convolution by bounding the filter coefficients:

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \right) \min_i \{\rho_i\}^l \leq |\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l| \leq \left(\sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \right) \max_i \{\rho_i\}^l \quad (28)$$

where $\min_i \{\rho_i\} = e^{\Delta \min_i \{\Re(\lambda_i)\}}$, and $\max_i \{\rho_i\} = e^{\Delta \max_i \{\Re(\lambda_i)\}}$.

Proof. Recall that the l -th element of the convolution filter is given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l = \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \rho_i^l \cos(\psi_i + l\theta_i),$$

where $\nu_i \geq 0$ is the amplitude, $\rho_i = e^{\Delta \Re(\lambda_i)}$ is the decay/growth factor, and ψ_i, θ_i are the phase and frequency parameters.

Since $|\cos(\psi_i + l\theta_i)| \leq 1$ for all i and l , we have

$$|\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l| \leq \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i |\rho_i|^l.$$

Moreover, since $\rho_i > 0$ for all i , we can bound the sum as

$$\sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \min_i \{\rho_i\}^l \leq \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \rho_i^l \leq \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \max_i \{\rho_i\}^l.$$

Thus,

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \right) \min_i \{\rho_i\}^l \leq |\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l| \leq \left(\sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \right) \max_i \{\rho_i\}^l.$$

To ensure stability (i.e., boundedness of the filter for all l), it is necessary that $\max_i \{\rho_i\} \leq 1$, which is equivalent to requiring $\Re(\lambda_i) \leq 0$ for all i . If $\Re(\lambda_i) < 0$, then $\rho_i < 1$ and the filter coefficients decay exponentially, resulting in fading memory. If $\Re(\lambda_i) = 0$, then $\rho_i = 1$ and the filter coefficients remain bounded but do not decay.

Therefore, the real part of the eigenvalues controls both the stability and the memory capacity of the convolution filter, as claimed.

Lemma 3: Parameter Scaling. The matrices \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C} control the oscillation amplitudes

$$\nu_i = |\bar{\mathbf{B}}_i| |\bar{\mathbf{C}}_i| \propto |\mathbf{B}_i| |\mathbf{C}_i| \in [m_{\mathbf{B}} m_{\mathbf{C}}, M_{\mathbf{B}} M_{\mathbf{C}}], \quad (29)$$

and the phase shifts

$$\psi_i = \arg(\bar{\mathbf{B}}_i) + \arg(\bar{\mathbf{C}}_i) \in [0, 2\pi). \quad (30)$$

Proof. Let $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{P \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times P}$ be the input and output matrices of the continuous SSM, with each entry of \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} having modulus in $[m_{\mathbf{B}}, M_{\mathbf{B}}]$ and $[m_{\mathbf{C}}, M_{\mathbf{C}}]$, respectively, where $m_{\mathbf{B}}, m_{\mathbf{C}}, M_{\mathbf{B}}, M_{\mathbf{C}} > 0$ (see Appendix C).

After discretization (e.g., via the ZOH method), the discrete parameters are

$$\bar{\mathbf{A}} = e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} (e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{B}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{C}.$$

The convolution kernel is given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}} = (\bar{\mathbf{C}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T) \cdot \mathbf{V},$$

where \mathbf{V} is the Vandermonde matrix of $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$. Define $\mathbf{W} = \bar{\mathbf{C}} \odot \bar{\mathbf{B}}^T$.

Expressing \mathbf{W} in polar form, each entry is $\mathbf{W}_i = \nu_i e^{i\psi_i}$, where $\nu_i = |\bar{\mathbf{B}}_i| |\bar{\mathbf{C}}_i|$ and $\psi_i = \arg(\bar{\mathbf{B}}_i \bar{\mathbf{C}}_i) = \arg(\bar{\mathbf{B}}_i) + \arg(\bar{\mathbf{C}}_i)$. Since $|\bar{\mathbf{B}}_i| \propto |\mathbf{B}_i| \in [m_{\mathbf{B}}, M_{\mathbf{B}}]$ and $|\bar{\mathbf{C}}_i| = |\mathbf{C}_i| \in [m_{\mathbf{C}}, M_{\mathbf{C}}]$, it follows that $[m_{\mathbf{B}} m_{\mathbf{C}}, M_{\mathbf{B}} M_{\mathbf{C}}]$ it give us an estimate of the amplitude ν_i . The phase ψ_i is in $[0, 2\pi)$ due to the randomness of $\arg(\mathbf{B}_i)$, and $\arg(\mathbf{C}_i)$ (see Appendix C).

Thus, the amplitude and phase of each oscillatory component in the convolution filter are directly determined by the magnitudes and arguments of the entries of $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$, as claimed.

Lemma 4 **Sampling Rate Effect.** The discretization step Δ affects the frequencies and decay:

$$\theta_i = \Delta \Im(\lambda_i), \quad \rho_i = e^{\Delta \Re(\lambda_i)}. \quad (31)$$

Larger Δ increases oscillation frequency but reduces memory capacity.

Proof. The Zero-Order Hold (ZOH) method discretizes the continuous-time SSM by sampling the input signal at intervals of Δ , i.e., $u_k = u(k\Delta)$, and assumes the signal is piecewise constant between samples:

$$u((k + \delta)\Delta) = u(k\Delta), \quad \delta \in [0, 1).$$

Under ZOH, the continuous SSM parameters ($\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{C}, \mathbf{D}$) are mapped to discrete parameters as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \bar{\mathbf{A}} = e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}} \\ \bar{\mathbf{B}} = \mathbf{A}^{-1} (e^{\Delta \mathbf{A}} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{B} \\ \bar{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{C} \\ \bar{\mathbf{D}} = \mathbf{D} \end{cases}$$

Let $\lambda_i = \Re(\lambda_i) + i\Im(\lambda_i)$ be the i -th eigenvalue of \mathbf{A} . The i -th eigenvalue of $\bar{\mathbf{A}}$ is $\bar{\lambda}_i = e^{\Delta \lambda_i} = e^{\Delta \Re(\lambda_i)} e^{i\Delta \Im(\lambda_i)}$. Thus, the modulus and argument are

$$\rho_i = |\bar{\lambda}_i| = e^{\Delta \Re(\lambda_i)}, \quad \theta_i = \arg(\bar{\lambda}_i) = \Delta \Im(\lambda_i).$$

The convolution filter is given by

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}}_l = \sum_{i=0}^{P-1} \nu_i \rho_i^l \cos(\psi_i + l\theta_i),$$

where ν_i and ψ_i are determined by $\bar{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{C}}$.

Therefore, the sampling rate Δ directly controls both the frequency and decay rate of each oscillatory component in the convolution filter, as claimed.

F Experimental Setup

In this appendix, we describe the architecture of our model for classification tasks and outline the models used as benchmarks.

To exploit the memory capacity of the RSSM and improve training efficiency, we employ two efficient readouts: an MLP and a ridge regressor, with the latter trained in closed form (Equations 13 14).

The model using the MLP readout is referred to as RSSM, while we denote the ridge regressor variant as RSSM-r. The readout learns dependencies between features within each timestep, independently of other timesteps, while the reservoir component of the RSSM captures temporal dependencies in the input sequences without requiring training.

Only the final timestep \mathbf{y}_{L-1} is used for classification tasks, as it encapsulates all previous states and best represents the entire sequence. The input dimension for the ridge regressor and the first MLP layer corresponds to the global output dimension of the RSSM, $n \cdot H$, where n is the number of RSSM layers, and H is the number of output sequence features per layer (see Section 3.2 and Figure 1). Each MLP layer uses the Gated Linear Unit (GLU) activation function, defined as:

$$GLU(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^{2N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \mathbf{a} \odot \sigma(\mathbf{b}), \quad (32)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid function. The GLU activation employs a gating mechanism that helps select important features, effectively halving the output dimensionality at each layer and controlling information flow, thus reducing readout complexity while retaining the most relevant features [15].

We evaluate our model’s performance against two fully trainable models, GRU and S4, and two reservoir computing models: a Leaky Integrator ESN [29] in its shallow configuration (referred as ESN) and deep configuration (referred as DeepESN) [17].

The ESN consists of a single layer, with the number of neurons matching the total number of hidden features in the RSSM with n layers. We configure the DeepESN with the same number of layers and neurons per layer. The states outputted from each layer of the DeepESN are concatenated, similar to our architecture (see Figure 1) [17]. Both ESN models use a closed-form ridge classifier for the readout, as in RSSM-r.

The GRU and S4 models are configured with comparable numbers of layers and hidden units to ensure fair efficiency comparisons. For reservoir-based models (ESN, RSSM-r, and RSSM), we set the batch size B as large as possible to optimize GPU efficiency, as the forward pass is independent of batch size. For training the MLP readout, we use a separate batch size B' , selected through model selection, similar to the approach used for fully trainable models (GRU and S4).

During the training phase of the MLP readout of RSSM and of the other models optimized with gradient descent, we split the development set into training and validation sets, using early stopping with a patience hyperparameter to prevent overfitting. After early stopping, we further train the model on the whole development set (training and validation combined) for a single epoch. We use the AdamW optimizer, which includes weight decay as a regularization hyperparameter. Additionally, a simple scheduler reduces the learning rate by

a factor if the validation loss does not decrease after reaching half the patience limit. Cross-entropy loss is used as the loss function.

F.1 Model Selection

This section details the approach used for hyperparameter tuning and selecting optimal model configurations.

For reservoir-based models (RSSM, RSSM-r, ESN, and DeepESN), which have untrained components, model selection is critical due to their sensitivity to hyperparameters and the large search space required. To address this, we employ random search, sampling up to 1000 configurations from the possible hyperparameter settings generated by a grid search. Unlike grid search, which systematically evaluates predefined combinations, random search allows for more efficient exploration of a broader range of configurations while reducing computational cost [5].

In contrast, for fully trainable models (GRU, S4), which are less sensitive to hyperparameter tuning, we use a traditional grid search approach.

Appendix G provides detailed tables outlining the hyperparameter space for each model.

To improve the efficiency of model selection for the RSSM model with ridge regression and MLP readouts, we leverage the modularity of the reservoir component and the independent processing of each of the H features. We implement a two-level model selection process to fully exploit these characteristics.

In the first phase, we select the best hyperparameters of the reservoir components of the RSSM by keeping the same ridge regression as readout (Table 9). We can fix the number of hidden features to a small enough value to enable a large batch size of B that does not change the result of the input processing due to the untrained reservoir. The combination of reduced model complexity (from the small H), large batch size, and the speed of the ridge classifier significantly accelerates the reservoir hyperparameter tuning. After identifying the optimal hyperparameters, we scale the reservoir component by increasing H to the desired size, and we generate the reservoir output, which serves as the readout dataset for the second phase.

In the second phase, we perform separate model selections for each readout – MLP (Table 11) and ridge regression (Table 10) – using the dataset from the selected reservoir. This allows us to fix the reservoir hyperparameters and focus on tuning the readouts.

By leveraging the independence of the H features arising from the H independent SSMs, the reservoir component scales with H . Additionally, the modularity of the reservoir component allows us to keep the same reservoir output for different readout models. These properties help mitigate the complexity of the hyperparameter space, making this two-level random search process both efficient and scalable.

Appendix H lists the final models for each task, along with the best hyperparameters obtained through the model selection. Specifically, Tables 16 and 17 show

the best hyperparameters selected for pixel-by-pixel and LRA tasks, respectively, for both RSSM and RSSM-r models.

F.2 Evaluation Metrics

In our experiments, we evaluate the accuracy of the time-series classification tasks and assess the model’s computational impact. Precisely, we measure the training time, carbon emissions, and energy consumption to comprehensively evaluate the environmental and resource costs associated with our approach. To achieve this, we use the CodeCarbon library [13]. The metrics collected include training time (measured in seconds), CO₂ emissions (measured in grams), and energy consumption (measured in kilowatt-hours, kWh). We conduct all experiments using the Tesla V100-PCIE-16GB GPU. By incorporating both accuracy and resource consumption metrics, our evaluation provides insight into the model’s predictive performance and the associated environmental costs, highlighting the trade-offs between computational demands and sustainability.

G Hyperparameter space

In this section, we provide details of the model selection, specifying the hyperparameter space for each model independently of the task. Tables 6 and 7 list the hyperparameters and their respective possible values for GRU and S4, respectively. Table 8 presents the hyperparameters and their possible values for both ESN and DeepESN.

Table 9 outlines the hyperparameters and their corresponding values for the reservoir component of RSSM. Lastly, Tables 10 and 11 list the hyperparameters and possible values for the ridge and MLP readouts of RSSM, respectively.

Table 6: GRU hyperparameter space for sMNIST, pMNIST, sCIFAR-10 tasks. "lr" and "wd" are, respectively, the learning rate and weight decay of AdamW. "rop" is the reducing factor of the learning rate on a validation score plateau.

GRU	hyperparameter values
batch size	{64, 128}
lr	{0.0005, 0.001, 0.005, 0.01}
wd	{0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5}
rop	0.2
patience	10

Table 7: S4 hyperparameter space for sMNIST, pMNIST and sCIFAR-10 tasks. "init" denotes the kernel structure. "num ssm" is the number of distinct SSM respect the total H independent SSM. "lr" and "wd" are, respectively, the learning rate and weight decay of AdamW. "rop" is the reducing factor of the learning rate on a validation score plateau. Further hyperparameter details are in [22].

S4	hyperparameter values
batch size	{64, 128}
state dim P	{64, 128, 256}
dropout	{0.0, 0.1, 0.2}
tie dropout	{False, True}
init	legs
m_{Δ}	0.001
M_{Δ}	0.1
kernel lr	0.001
kernel wd	0.0
bidirectional	{False, True}
final act	$GLU(\cdot)$
num ssm	{1, 2, 8, 64}
lr	{0.0005, 0.001, 0.005, 0.01}
wd	{0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5}
rop	0.2
patience	10

Table 8: ESN and DeepESN hyperparameter space for sMNIST, pMNIST and sCIFAR-10 tasks. *input scaling* is the scaling factor of the input weight matrix, ρ is the spectral radius of the recurrent weight matrix, and *leaky* is the leaking rate [43, 17]. *ridge α* is the ridge parameter of Thikonov regularization for the offline training (Equation [13]).

ESN/DeepESN hyperparameter values	
<i>batch size B</i>	as large as possible
<i>input scaling</i>	{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 1.0}
<i>bias scaling</i>	{0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 1.0}
ρ	{0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 1.1}
<i>leaky</i>	{0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1.0}
<i>ridge α</i>	{0.0, 0.4, 0.8, 1.5, 3.0, 5.0, 7.5, 10.0, 12.5, 15.0}

Table 9: Hyperparameter space of the RSSM reservoir component for sMNIST, pMNIST, sCIFAR-10, and LRA tasks. The hyperparameters of the RSSM reservoir component are described in [C.1](#), *ridge* α is the ridge parameter of Thikonov regularization for the offline training (Equation [13](#)). We fix the ridge regressor readout while selecting the RSSM reservoir component with small $H = 64$ as described in [F.1](#).

RSSM	hyperparameter values
<i>features</i> H	64
<i>batch size</i> B	as large as possible
<i>state dim</i> P	{8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024}
$\phi_{fwd}(\cdot)$	$ReLU(\cdot)$
$\phi_{fit}(\cdot)$	$TanH(\cdot)$
$m_{\mathbf{w}_{en}}$	0.0
$M_{\mathbf{w}_{en}}$	{0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25}
<i>discrete</i>	False
$m_{\mathbf{A}}$	{-4.5, -4.0, -3.5, -3.0, -2.5, -2.0, -1.5, -1.0, -0.5, 0.0}
$M_{\mathbf{A}}$	{-0.5, 0.0}
m_{Δ}	{0.0001, 0.0005, 0.001, 0.005, 0.01}
M_{Δ}	{0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.005, 0.1}
$m_{\mathbf{B}}$	0.0
$M_{\mathbf{B}}$	{0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25}
$m_{\mathbf{C}}$	0.0
$M_{\mathbf{C}}$	{0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.25}
$m_{\mathbf{D}}$	{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0}
$M_{\mathbf{D}}$	{0.0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0}
<i>ridge</i> α	0.8

Table 10: Ridge regressor hyperparameter space for sMNIST, pMNIST, sCIFAR-10, and LRA tasks. α is the ridge parameter of Thikonov regularization for the offline training (Equation [13](#)).

ridge regression hyperparameter values	
α	{0.0, 0.4, 0.8, 1.5, 3.0, 5.0, 7.5, 10.0, 12.5, 15.0}

Table 11: MLP hyperparameter space for sMNIST, pMNIST, sCIFAR-10, and LRA tasks. For sMNIST and pMNIST, the number of layers is fixed at 2 due to the lower complexity of the task. lr and wd are, respectively, the learning rate and weight decay of AdamW. rop is the reducing factor of the learning rate on a validation score plateau.

MLP	hyperparameter values
$layers$	{2, 4, 6}
$batch\ size\ B'$	{64, 128}
lr	{0.0005, 0.001, 0.005, 0.01}
wd	{0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5}
rop	0.2
$patience$	10

H Best hyperparameters

In this section, we present the best models selected through the model selection process for each model and task (Section F.1 and Appendix G).

Tables 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 show the optimal hyperparameter values for GRU, S4, ESN, DeepESN, and RSSM models, respectively, across the sMNIST, pMNIST, and sCIFAR-10 tasks.

Table 17 presents the optimal hyperparameter values for the RSSM models on the LRA tasks.

Table 12: GRU best hyperparameters for sMNIST, pMNIST, and sCIFAR-10 tasks selected from Table 6

GRU	sMNIST	pMNIST	sCIFAR-10
$layers$	2	2	6
$features\ P$	256	256	512
$batch$	128	128	64
lr	0.001	0.001	0.001
wd	0.1	0.1	0.1
rop	0.2	0.2	0.2
$patience$	10	10	10

Table 13: S4 best hyperparameters for sMNIST and pMNIST, and sCIFAR-10 tasks selected from Table 7

S4	sMNIST	pMNIST	sCIFAR-10
layers	2	2	6
features H	256	256	512
batch	128	128	64
state dim P	64	64	64
dropout	0.1	0.1	0.1
tie dropout	True	True	True
init	legs	legs	legs
m_Δ	0.001	0.001	0.001
M_Δ	0.1	0.1	0.1
kernel lr	0.001	0.001	0.001
kernel wd	0.0	0.0	0.0
bidirectional	True	True	True
final act	$GLU(\cdot)$	$GLU(\cdot)$	$GLU(\cdot)$
num ssm	1	1	2
lr	0.01	0.01	0.01
wd	0.05	0.05	0.05
rop	0.2	0.2	0.2
patience	10	10	10

Table 14: ESN best hyperparameters for sMNIST, pMNIST, and sCIFAR-10 tasks selected from Table 8

ESN	sMNIST	pMNIST	sCIFAR-10
features $H \equiv P$	2048	2048	16384
batch B	256	256	32
input scaling	0.3	0.1	0.5
bias scaling	0.0	0.0	0.7
rho	1.1	1.0	1.0
leaky	0.5	1.0	0.1
ridge α	0.4	0.4	12.5

Table 15: DeepESN best hyperparameters for sMNIST, pMNIST, and sCIFAR-10 tasks selected from Table 8

DeepESN	sMNIST	pMNIST	sCIFAR-10
layers	2	2	8
features $H \equiv P$	1024	1024	2048
batch B	256	256	32
input scaling	0.3	0.1	0.6
bias scaling	0.1	0.0	0.4
rho	1.0	1.0	1.0
leaky	0.2	1.0	0.7
ridge α	0.4	0.4	15.0

Table 16: RSSM-r and RSSM best hyperparameters for sMNIST, pMNIST, and sCIFAR-10 tasks. The first block of hyperparameters corresponds to the reservoir component, the second to the ridge readout, and the third to the MLP readout. The optimal hyperparameters for the reservoir, ridge readout, and MLP readout are selected from Tables 9, 10, and 11, respectively.

RSSM	sMNIST	pMNIST	sCIFAR-10
layers n	2	2	8
features H	1024	1024	2048
batch B	256	256	32
state dim P	512	256	64
$\phi_{fwd}(\cdot)$	$ReLU(\cdot)$	$ReLU(\cdot)$	$ReLU(\cdot)$
$\phi_{fit}(\cdot)$	$TanH(\cdot)$	$TanH(\cdot)$	$TanH(\cdot)$
$m_{W_{en}}$	0.0	0.0	0.0
$M_{W_{en}}$	0.25	0.75	0.75
discrete	False	False	False
$m_{\mathbf{A}}$	-3.5	-2.5	0.0
$M_{\mathbf{A}}$	0.0	0.0	0.0
m_{Δ}	0.0001	0.0005	0.0001
M_{Δ}	0.1	0.1	0.1
$m_{\mathbf{B}}$	0.0	0.0	0.0
$M_{\mathbf{B}}$	1.25	0.75	0.75
$M_{\mathbf{C}}$	1.0	0.75	0.1
$m_{\mathbf{D}}$	0.25	0.0	0.25
$M_{\mathbf{D}}$	0.75	0.75	1.0
ridge α	0.0	0.0	12.5
MLP layers	2	2	6
batch B'	128	128	64
lr	0.005	0.005	0.0005
wd	0.1	0.1	0.5
rop	0.2	0.2	0.2
patience	10	10	10

Table 17: RSSM-r and RSSM best hyperparameters for LRA tasks. The first block of hyperparameters corresponds to the reservoir component, the second to the ridge readout, and the third to the MLP readout. The optimal hyperparameters for the reservoir, ridge readout, and MLP readout are selected from Tables [9](#), [10](#) and [11](#), respectively.

RSSM	Image	ListOps	Text	Pathfinder	Path-X
layers n	8	8	8	8	8
features H	2048	2048	2048	2048	2048
batch B	32	32	8	32	4
state dim P	1024	512	256	64	128
$\phi_{fwd}(\cdot)$	<i>ReLU</i> (\cdot)				
$\phi_{fit}(\cdot)$	<i>TanH</i> (\cdot)				
$m_{W_{en}}$	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
$M_{W_{en}}$	0.25	0.25	1.25	1.0	0.5
discrete	False	False	False	False	False
m_A	-2.5	-0.5	-1.0	0.0	-1.5
M_A	0.0	-0.5	-0.5	0.0	0.0
m_Δ	0.01	0.001	0.0001	0.01	0.0001
M_Δ	0.1	0.01	0.001	0.1	0.001
m_B	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
M_B	0.5	1.0	1.25	0.25	1.25
m_C	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
M_C	0.75	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5
m_D	0.5	0.0	0.75	1.0	0.0
M_D	1.0	0.25	1.0	1.0	1.0
ridge α	12.5	0.8	15.0	1.5	0.4
MLP layers	6	4	2	4	4
batch B'	64	64	64	64	64
lr	0.001	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005
wd	0.5	0.01	0.1	0.5	0.1
rop	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
patience	10	10	10	10	10

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